

Orphan Drugs

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ABSTRACT

Investors undertake the time-consuming and costly program of drug development that transforms a potential drug candidate into a marketable medicine, only if it promises a good amount of return within a short time. A drug used for the clinical management of a rare disease does not attract the attention of investors because of the low return it provides. Such neglected drugs are called orphan drugs. Governments in some places give a number of concessions and incentives for the development of orphan drugs, so that they can survive competition with high-selling drugs. The possible role of repurposed drugs in dealing with the problems of rare diseases is also highlighted.

Keywords: Orphan drugs, Rare diseases, Snakebite, Incentives, Repurposed drug

Drug development: A time-consuming and costly program

The story of the serendipitous discovery of penicillin is well-known to us. It is noteworthy that it took more than a decade to develop the culture filtrate with antibacterial activity discovered by Sir Alexander Fleming into a usable medicine. Even in the present scenario, notwithstanding the leaps and bounds in progress in the field of science and technology witnessed during the last century, we have to traverse through a long procedure involving preclinical research, clinical research, regulatory review, and post-market safety monitoring to get a therapeutically useful antibacterial medicine out of a crude culture filtrate. The whole process of drug development remains time-consuming and costly as it was before.

What makes a drug orphan?

After some promising therapeutic activity is discovered in a crude plant extract, an unpurified chemical or a bacterial culture filtrate, if nobody comes forward to undertake the financially risky program of drug development, the crude drug never takes the shape of a formulation, which is widely available in the open market. A drug that

does not find an entrepreneur to develop into a pharmaceutical formulation is called an orphan drug [1].

Drugs become orphan simply because of the financial burden associated with their development. The industrialists do not find it profitable to manufacture a pharmaceutical formulation on a large scale if the new product does not appear to attract a sufficient number of users. We know various factors are responsible for the low rate of sales of a drug. The low rate of prevalence of the disease for which the drug is meant is one of them. Thus, the drugs for rare diseases remain neglected. Most of the industrialists do not show any interest in manufacturing and distributing them on a wide scale. They feel discouraged to invest over \$2 billion and wait for 10-15 years for the development of a new drug that would be used only by a small number of patients [2].

Examples of rare diseases in the US

Certain diseases are found to be rare in some particular populations. Cystic Fibrosis is a genetic disorder causing thick mucus buildup, leading to lung and digestive issues. Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy is a muscle-wasting disease. Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) is a neurodegenerative

disease of the nerve cells that control muscle movement. Fabry's Disease is a metabolic disorder leading to the buildup of a fatty substance in cells. Huntington's Disease is a hereditary disease characterised by progressive breakdown of nerve cells in the brain [3]. These are some examples of rare diseases found in the US.

Examples of rare diseases in India

Haemophilia, thalassemia, sickle-cell anaemia, various lysosomal storage disorders (LSDs: e.g., Gaucher and Fabry's disease), cystic fibrosis, and some muscular dystrophies are rare genetic disorders among the Indians. Endogamy (marriage within the same community) is believed to contribute to the higher risk for such diseases in certain populations of Indians. Mental retardation is constantly present in severe forms of mucopolysaccharidoses, a group of genetic diseases. Individually, the disease is considered rare.

For quite some time, cystic fibrosis was also believed to be a rare medical problem in India. Evidences available at present indicate that the problem in many cases remains underdiagnosed because of a lack of awareness and facilities. The actual frequency of this disease among the Indians remains unknown. Limited access of the rural population to advanced diagnostic facilities and the high cost of treatment make the situation more problematic in this country.

Droxia (Hydroxyurea) used in the clinical management of sickle-cell anaemia requires storage at 20 °C to 25 °C. In March 2024, Akum Drugs and Pharmaceuticals launched India's first indigenous room-temperature stable Hydroxyurea oral suspension at 1 per cent of the global price. Needless to say, it will significantly improve the affordability and availability of the drug to the patients of sickle-cell anaemia [4].

Some other factors that define the status of a drug

A medical problem may earn the status of an orphan disease for various other reasons. Tuberculosis (TB), though rampant in the developing world, is found to occur in low frequency in Western Europe, North

America, Australia and New Zealand, according to a study published on PubMed Central. Problems of malnutrition and poor sanitation systems that promote prevalence and dissemination of the tubercular infection are less prevalent in these countries. Quite reasonably, TB is a disease with low occurrence, and the demand for the anti-tubercular drugs is also low in this part of the world. Drugs used for the prevention and clinical management of TB are less likely to give a good return if marketed in the above-mentioned countries. Thus, they are likely to be branded as orphans in these healthy populations.

Orphan status of a drug because of difficulty in production

Snakebite is one of the major causes of death in India. Approximately 45900 to 50000 deaths are reported to occur every year as a result of snakebites, according to a study published by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Press Information Bureau (PIB). The antivenin, widely used for the clinical management of snakebite in India, consists of a mixture of antibodies raised in some experimental animals (horses or mules) against the venoms of the four most frequently occurring poisonous snakes known as "Big Four" (Russell's viper, common krait, Indian cobra, and Indian saw-scaled viper). If a person is bitten by a venomous snake belonging to some other category, the doctors find it challenging to save the life of the victim in the absence of the required antibody. Production of the antibody, active against the venom of some other snake (outside the Big Four category), is difficult for various reasons. These life-saving remedies remain orphaned because of the dearth of industrialists who could undertake their production. The choice of remedy for the bite of a snake other than the "Big Four" has to be compromised. The antivenin prepared against the "Big Four" types of venomous snakes has to be used in the absence of the right antivenin, making the prospect of recovery uncertain.

Concession given to orphan drugs by the government

Needless to say, the lack of interest of the industrialists in developing new drugs is not a healthy trend for society. In order to encourage the pharmaceutical companies to produce the orphan drugs, the governments of different places give some concessions or incentives, including research grants, tax credits for clinical trials, and fee reductions for regulatory submissions. The manufacturers get a market exclusivity of 5-10 years during which no other manufacturer is allowed to produce the drug. In order to meet the expenses of the clinical trial, the manufacturer may get a 50% tax credit. The regulatory agency may expedite the review process and reduce some fees; the agency also offers help by providing scientific guidance.

Antibiotics as an orphan drug

Some antibiotics have gained the status of orphan drugs since they are required only by some patients who contract some rare infections, which are curable by the antibiotics. MRX-5, a novel benzoxazole antibiotic manufactured by MicuRx Pharmaceuticals, is an orphan drug in the US. It is being developed for the treatment of drug-resistant infection of non-tuberculous mycobacteria (NTM). Omadacycline, an aminomethylcycline antibiotic, also has the status of an orphan drug from the FDA for the treatment of NTM infections caused by *Mycobacterium abscessus* complex.

Repurposed drug

If a drug, originally developed for a particular purpose, is identified with a new therapeutic use, it is called a repurposed drug. At present, only 5% of the total 6000 to 8000 rare diseases are known to have an approved treatment option [5]. Development of new drugs for the rare diseases is challenging because of various problems such as limited patient populations, disease complexity and lack of understanding of disease pathobiology and high development costs. In this backdrop, the repurposing of some existing drugs appears to be time and cost-

efficient. Various examples of drug repurposing are already available in clinical practice. Sildenafil, once widely used for the treatment of angina pectoris, is used at present for the treatment of pulmonary hypertension. Propranolol, used once upon a time for clinical management of hypertension, is used at present for infantile hemangioma (tumour of the blood vessel). The anti-cancer drug methotrexate is found to be useful for the management of different types of inflammation and autoimmune diseases. Alpelisib, originally developed for some breast cancers, is now being investigated for its possible use in the management of PIK3CA-related overgrowth spectrum (PROS). A guidebook published by the International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDiRC, a global public/private collaborative initiative launched in 2011 by the European Commission and the US National Institutes of Health), focuses on repurposing approaches.

Conclusion

It is obvious from the foregoing discussion that orphan drugs are a challenging problem in clinical practice with several socioeconomic issues associated with them. It appears that the government should be more active in increasing the availability and affordability of orphan drugs to the common people.

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Declaration of competing interests

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References

1. Definition of orphan drug-Definition – NCI Dictionary of Cancer Terms. National Cancer Institute.
2. Aronson JR (2006) Rare diseases and orphan drugs *Br J Clin. Pharmacol.* Mar; 61(3):243–245.
3. Randhawa K (2006). Orphan diseases and drugs. *Ind. J.Pharmacol.* 38 (3)171-176.

4. Akums launches room temperature stable oral suspension of Hydroxyurea to treat SCD. Express Pharma. March 20, 2024. Reports collected from the Internet.
5. Jonker AH et al (2024). Drug repurposing for rare: Progress and opportunities for the rare disease community. Front Med (Lausanne) Jan 17;11:1352803.